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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**5-Civic Engagement as a Driver of Political
Change in Post-Totalitarian States. Vitalii
Kostenko and others. p. 104.**

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**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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Contents of Vol. No. (47/2) of Issue October-2025

- 1- **International Security Cooperation of Ukraine in The Face of The Russian-Ukrainian War: Factors of Historical and Legal Aspects.** By Yurii Rusnak and others. p. 10.
- 2- **Global Strategic Rivalry and the Secure Architecture: Nato's Influence on The Formation of The International Peace,** By Yevhenii Taran. and others. p. 30.
- 3- **Multipolarity of the Global Space: Strategic Understanding of Geopolitical Trends.** By Viacheslav Kolotov and others. p. 55.
- 4- **Mechanisms for Restoring Violated Rights to Intellectual Products: Law Enforcement Difficulties in Ukraine.** By Viktoriia Kobko-Odarii and others. p. 82.
- 5- **Civic Engagement as a Driver of Political Change in Post-Totalitarian States.** Vitalii Kostenko and others. p. 104.
- 6- **International Humanitarian Law Implications During the War in Ukraine: Problems and Violations.** By Oleksandr Khomenko and others. p. 123.
- 7- **Russian-Ukrainian War's Geopolitical Consequences for Eastern Europe.** By Vira Kazymir and others. p. 138.
- 8- **Constitutional Rights and Freedoms of Citizens: Problems of Protection And Implementation In Ukraine.** By Denys Chyzhov . And others. P. 154.
- 9- **Criminal Liability for Economic Crimes: Issues of Legal Qualification And Application In Practice.** By Volodymyr Myslyvyy and others. p. 176.
- 10- **The Dynamics of Public-Private Interaction in Advancing Sustainable Development Through Investment Strategies and Administration.** By Myroslav Buryk and others. p. 198.
- 11- **Cooperation of Governmental Institutions And Advocacy Associations Within the Framework of The Fundamental Freedoms: Conceptual Perspective.** By Olena Bondarchuk- Ladna and others. p. 228.
- 12- **The Issue of Criminal Liability for Corruption Crimes in The Context of Legal Modernization.** By Anfisa Serhiienko and others. p. 250.
- 13- **Anti-Corruption Policy and Its Administration in Public Administration: Theoretical Foundations and Practical Aspects of the Legal Framework.** By Oleksii Vasyliiev and others. p. 276.
- 14- **Electoral Behavioral Models in Sweden and Norway: A Psychopolitical Perspective.** By Viktor Melnyk and others. p. 299.
- 15- **The Evolution of Legal Frameworks in Lithuanian State Formation: Historical Perspectives -and The Impact of European Integration.** By Lesia Kotsur and others. p. 325.
- 16- **Public Debt and Public Debt Administration Under Martial Law in the Process of Post-War Reconstruction,** By Serhii Petrukha and others. p. 341.
- 17- **Global Economic Interaction as a Factor of Innovative Progress in Countries with A Transformational Model of Growth.** By Yevhenii Kostyk and others. p. 372,

(5)

CIVIC ENGAGEMENT AS A DRIVER OF POLITICAL CHANGE IN POST- TOTALITARIAN STATES

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ABSTRACT

In post-communist countries, democratic transformations are characterized by a complex heterogeneous structure, depending on public participation in the transition to democratic values, active or passive participation of citizens in electoral processes. The purpose of this article is to study the impact of civil society on the processes of democratic transition in post-communist countries. The methodology of

the article is based on a comparative analysis and grouping of post-communist countries by the Democracy and Civil Society Development Indices (DCI) in 1990-2024. The results demonstrate that there is a link between a high level of democracy (Estonia, Lithuania, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Latvia, Romania, Poland, Croatia) and a high level of civil society involvement in political life in these countries, as well as the resilience and active position of citizens. In countries that have chosen the European course of development, despite the support of the population, democratic transition has been faster and the political situation has stabilized. Instead, in countries where there is external political pressure and involvement (Ukraine, Moldova, Serbia, Georgia), the active role of society contributed to reforms, although these countries are still in the process of transition and the establishment of democratic values. Civil society in countries with hybrid regimes acts as an agent of pressure on the authorities and support for reforms, but is limited by internal political instability and external influence. At the same time, the role of civil society in these countries is growing, despite a significant gap with countries with a high degree of democratization. The influence of civil society organizations (further – CSOs) in this region remains at an average level, in the form of public control, digitalization and development of e-democracy, and anti-corruption initiatives. The absence of an independent judiciary hinders the development of civil society (further – CS). In countries with authoritarian regimes, the role of civil society is rather limited, which leads to its weak influence on political decisions, weakness of the democratic transition, and repressive policies towards civic activists.

Keywords: *civil society, civil society participation, democracy, democratic transition, democratic institutions, post-communist countries, socialist regimes.*

1- INTRODUCTION

After the collapse of socialist regimes in Central and Eastern Europe (further – CEE), the Balkan countries and the post-Soviet space, a large-scale wave of political changes and reforms aimed at establishing democratic institutions, the rule of law and pluralistic governance began.

Transition to a democratic political system in post-communist countries requires reforming the legal system, establishing the legal state and the rule of law principle, ensuring the right to express ones opinions, free citizen's participation in political decision-making, decentralization of power and the formation of institutions of power separation.

In post-communist countries, democratic transformations have a complex heterogeneous structure, dependent on public participation in the transition to democratic values, and active or passive participation of citizens in electoral processes. The institutionalization of civil society determines the ability to form sustainable, society-oriented state institutions and ensure public participation in public administration. The purpose of this article is to study the impact of civil society on the democratic transition processes in post-communist countries.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Scholars in academic discussions continues to view civil society in post-communist countries as a factor in the transition to democracy¹. At the same time, most scholars emphasize the weakness of the CS compared to other regions of Europe, as well as the high expectations of its importance in democratization since the beginning of 1989-1991^{2, 3, 4}. Researchers especially relate this focus to expectations of the growing strength and dynamic development of this phenomenon subsequent to the end of communist regime⁵. The fragility of civil society in post-communist states is commonly attributed to the enduring legacy of communism – manifested in citizens reluctance to participate voluntary in organizations – and to the persistence impact of ethnic nationalism⁶.

As noted by Howard⁷, in different regions with “old” democratic regimes, or post-communist systems, post-communist states have relatively lower levels of CS organization and membership. This indicates that there are differences in the development of civic participation and activism between these groups of states⁸. At the same time, post-communist countries still form a coherent cluster of states with common characteristics for this region. The instability of the post-communist democracy until the early 2000s hindered the formation of civic capacities vital for reinforcing and sustaining democratic governance⁹. Scholars believed that post-communist citizens lacked sufficient institutional representation and the political

¹ Bolleyer, N., & Correa, P. (2022). Member influence and involvement in civil society organizations: A resource dependency perspective on groups and parties. *Political Studies*, 70(2), 519-540. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0032321720968018>

² Guasti, P. (2016). A Panacea for Democratic Legitimation? Assessing the Engagement of Civil Society with EU Treaty Reform Politics. In *Democratising the EU from Below?* (pp. 135-163). Routledge. <https://www.soc.cas.cz/en/publications/panacea-democratic-legitimation-assessing-engagement-civil-society-eu-treaty-reform>

³ Chimiak, G. (2021). The internationalization of Polish civil society elites and their impact on development cooperation policy and practice. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 41(5/6), 748-761. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSSP-06-2020-0208>

⁴ Pierobon, C. (2021). European Union, civil society and local ownership in Kyrgyzstan: analysing patterns of adaptation, reinterpretation and contestation in the prevention of violent extremism (PVE). *Central Asian Survey*, 41(4), 752-769. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02634937.2021.1905608>

⁵ Howard, M. M. (2002). The weakness of postcommunist civil society. *Journal of democracy*, 13(1), 157-169. <https://doi.org/10.1353/jod.2002.0008>

⁶ Kostovicova, D. (2006). Civil society and post-communist democratization: Facing a double challenge in post-Milošević Serbia. *Journal of Civil Society*, 2(1), 21-37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448680600730918>

⁷ Howard, M. M. (2002). *Id.*

⁸ Stan, L. (2012). Civil society and post-communist transitional justice in Romania. In *Transitional justice and civil society in the Balkans* (pp. 17-31). New York: Springer New York. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-5422-9_2

⁹ Howard, M. M. (2002). *Id.*

“leverage” that volunteer organizations could provide through their activity^{10, 11}. However, since the beginning of 2004-2005, the active processes of European integration have significantly transformed the role of CSOs in the democratic transition.

Contrary to the conventional perception of civil society’s weakness, Bernhard and Kaya¹² provide evidence that it has functioned as a significant material force in driving democratic transitions in post-communist states. This work challenges the prevailing tendency to characterize post-communist civil society in binary terms as being robust or fragile. Instead, the authors demonstrate the differences in the strength of CS influence in the transitional periods of countries’ development¹³.

According to Green¹⁴ post-communist society plays a crucial role in the democratic transformation following authoritarian rule. Despite the importance and common academic perception of CS as a factor of aggregation and reflection of common interests of the population, there are limitations in the study of its role in different groups of post-communist countries. Bernhard and Jung¹⁵ contend that the robustness of civil society during the transition to from communist strongly predicts the emergence of liberal democratic regimes in post-communist states due to the active role civil society plays in restructuring political elites¹⁶. Ekiert¹⁷ note that CS organizations have a manageable impact on democratic transition. Pietrzyk-Reeves¹⁸ contends that civil society in CEE countries ought to be examined as a cause or outcome of democratization and democratic consolidation, but as an autonomous phenomenon. Baća¹⁹, Kákai and Bejma²⁰ study the role of CSOs in post-communist societies and the controversial practices of their activities.

¹⁰ Jacobsson, K., & Korolczuk, E. (2017). *Civil society revisited: Lessons from Poland*. Berghahn Books. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvw04jx2>

¹¹ Sellers, J. M., Lidström, A., & Bae, Y. (2020). *Multilevel democracy: How local institutions and civil society shape the modern state*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108672337>

¹² Bernhard, M., & Kaya, R. (2012). Civil society and regime type in European post-communist countries: The perspective two decades after 1989-1991. *Taiwan Journal of Democracy*, 8(2), 113-126. <https://doi.org/10.29654/TJD.201212.0011>

¹³ Bernhard, M., & Kaya, R. (2012). *Id.*

¹⁴ Green, A. T. (2002). Comparative development of post-communist civil societies. *Europe-Asia Studies*, 54(3), 455-471. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09668130220129560>

¹⁵ Bernhard, M., & Jung, D. J. (2017). Civil society and income inequality in post-communist Eurasia. *Comparative Politics*, 49(3), 373-397. <https://doi.org/10.5129/001041517820934249>

¹⁶ Bernhard, M., & Jung, D. J. (2017). *Id.*

¹⁷ Ekiert, G., (2021). Civil society as a threat to democracy. *In The power of populism and people: Resistance and protest in the modern world* (pp. 53-71). <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781350211452.0007>

¹⁸ Pietrzyk-Reeves, D. (2022). Rethinking theoretical approaches to civil society in Central and Eastern Europe: Toward a dynamic approach. *East European Politics and Societies*, 36(4), 1335-1354. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08883254221081037>

¹⁹ Baća, B. (2022). Practice theory and postsocialist civil society: Toward a new analytical framework. *International Political Sociology*, 16(1), olab021. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ips/olab021>

Foa and Ekiert²¹ have a different position on the post-communist HS. The authors point out that since the early 2000s, civil society in this region has been structurally imperfect. At the same time, after the establishment of democracy, active, strong and mobilized civil society movements of the transition period became much weaker²². In the post-communist space, scholars observed divergent political trajectories, although the structure of CS in this region was weak. Overall, the new dataset demonstrates reveals that civil societies in CEE are stronger than traditionally assumed. Many post-communist countries are quite active in the public sphere of expression. Active CSOs closely interconnected with transnational civil society networks that are able to influence and shape the domestic policies of these countries. Based on the study of different models of CS, scientists found that social and civil institutions are capable to influence the divergent transitions paths between post-communist states. Specifically, researchers observed a widening divide between the democratic oriented countries in CEE and the increasingly authoritarian post-Soviet region²³.

Ishkanian²⁴ highlights the unintended effects of top-down democracy promotion strategies on the growth of post-socialist society. External democracy promotion programs have often resulted in donor-driven governance of non-governmental organizations, which remain accountable primarily to their founders rather than to their own communities and constituencies²⁵. As Stoltzfus and Osmar²⁶ point out, recent years have witnessed the emergence of populist and authoritarian styles of governance and, in response, a rise in popular activism.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study analyzes quantitative indicators of democracy and civil society raise in post-communist countries, specifically, examining the interrelationship between political rights, civil liberties, and citizen engagement indexes from 1990 to 2024.

²⁰ Kákai, L., & Bejma, A. (2022). Legal and practical conditions of the functioning of the civil society organizations in Hungary and Poland. *Eastern Journal of European Studies*, 13, 120-139. <https://doi.org/10.47743/ejes-2022-S107>

²¹ Foa, R. S., & Ekiert, G. (2016). The weakness of postcommunist civil society reassessed. *European Journal of Political Research*, 56(2), 419-439. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12182>

²² Ost, D. (2012). The decline of civil society after 'post-communism'. In *The new politics of European civil society* (pp. 163-177). Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780203836682-12/decline-civil-society-post-communism-david-ost>

²³ Foa, R. S., & Ekiert, G. (2016). *Id.*

²⁴ Ishkanian, A. (2014). Engineered civil society: The impact of 20 years of democracy promotion on civil society development in former soviet countries. In *Civil society and democracy promotion* (pp. 150-170). London: Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137291097_8

²⁵ Ishkanian, A. (2014). *Id.*

²⁶ Stoltzfus, N., & Osmar, C. (2021). *The power of populism and people: Resistance and protest in the modern world*. London: Bloomsbury Academic. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781350211452>

For the comparative analysis of post-communist countries by the level of democratization and their clustering, the Political Rights Index (A) and the Civil Liberties Index (B) for 2024, which are available in the Variety of Democracy database (V-Dem Institute, n.d.), were used. Given that the values of these indices were normalized from 0 to 1, the k-means clustering method based on the average value allowed us to identify countries with a high level of democratization, countries with transitional/hybrid political regimes, and countries with authoritarian regimes.

To assess the development of civil society and its contribution in democratic change, the following indices were used: The Civil Society Participation Index to assess the level of citizens' involvement in civic organizations, women's participation, and consultations with non-profit organizations; the Civil Liberties Index; the Deliberative Democracy Index; and the Electoral Democracy Index (Table 1). The scores of the respective Indices are available in the Variety of Democracy database²⁷ for 1990-2024. Researchers computed the average Index scores for 1990-2024 to classify post-communist countries and compare them based on the level of development of the CS. As a result, paper identify countries with a three level of civil society development: low level (scores of 0 – 0.3), an average level (scores of 0.31 – 0.6), and a high level (scores of more than 0.61 – 1).

The CCSI Civil Society Index assesses the level of autonomy, resilience of society, citizen engagement, and interaction with the authorities at the national/local level of government to achieve their own interests and collective goals.

Table 1. Democracy and Civil Society Indices

Index	Characteristics and significance
Civil Society Participation Index (0 – low, 1 – high) represents point estimates derived from a Bayesian factor analysis model. It incorporate indicators such as selection of legislative bodies at both national and local levels, consultation with CSOs, the environment for CSO participation, and participation of women in CSOs	Regularity of consultations of politicians with major civil society organizations, level of public participation in CSOs, restriction or support of women's participation in CSOs, extend to which candidates nominations for legislative bodies An indicator of the civil society sustainability, its level of independence from central government, the activity and freedom of citizens in achieving civic/political goals
Civil liberties index (0 – low, 1 – high): reflects the average value of the political civil liberties index, the physical violence index, and the private civil liberties index	Liberal freedom refers to individual rights characterized by the absence of state-inflicted physical violence and the lack of limitations on private and political freedoms The level of restrictions on citizens by

²⁷ V-Dem Institute. (n.d.). V-Dem Yearly Variable Graph Tool. https://v-dem.net/data_analysis/VariableGraph/

	the authorities
Deliberative Democracy Index (0 = low, 1 = high): The index is aggregated to include the electoral democracy indicator	It characterizes decision-making processes in the state system; deliberative processes mean the focus of public thinking on the common good, motivation for political decisions in favor of citizens Taking into account the interests of citizens in the implementation of governance
Electoral democracy index (0 – low, 1 – high): calculated as an average and weighted average to aggregate indices characterizing association freedom, speech freedom, fair elections, public chosen representatives and voting right	Electoral democracy is seen as a component of deliberative democracy The level of consideration of citizens' opinions by the government, which is achieved through electoral competition for the approval of the electorate, provided that the electoral law is sufficient, political and public associations are free to act, and there is no electoral fraud or systematic violations

Source: summarized by the author of V-Dem Institute²⁸

The Civil Liberties Index is used to assess the level of restrictions on citizens by the authorities, including private and political freedom. The Deliberative Democracy Index measures how well politician's decision serve the interests of citizens and the consideration of their interests in public administration. The Electoral Democracy Index complements previous assessments of a country's democracy by determining the level of consideration by the government of the civil society opinions, with regard to free elections and the activities of political and public associations.

4. RESULTS

Universal human value priorities are the fundamental higher principles for ensuring the development of democracy, national economy, European integration and political and economic convergence of countries. The introduction of democratic institutional changes and principles through the processes of European integration, liberalization, democratization, and competition have a positive impact on the participation of citizens in social development. The fundamental values of democracy, freedom, human rights, and social equality are more widespread in free countries, which ensures high involvement of citizens in the political life of the country.

The level of freedom and democracy in the CEE countries, the Baltic States, the Balkan countries, and post-Soviet countries is significantly differentiated depending on the depth of democratic reforms, participation in European integration processes, the

²⁸ V-Dem Institute. (n.d.). *Id.*

effectiveness and efficiency of public administration institutions, foreign and domestic policy, and the level of civic influence on democratization processes. These factors have determined the establishment of post-communist countries as liberal democracies, the degree of authoritarianism, or the duration of the transition to a democratic political regime.

The results of clustering countries by level of democracy show that Estonia, Lithuania, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Latvia (A and B) have the highest scores for freedom, and Poland, Romania, and Croatia have consistently high scores (Figure 1). These countries have a high degree of political rights and civil liberties. After the 1990s, the Civil Society Participation Index in Lithuania, Latvia, and Estonia increased from a value of 0.08 in 1990 to 0.64 in 2024. In Romania, the index was 0.58 in 1990, reaching 0.8 in 2015 and decreasing to 0.53 in 2024. Poland had the highest Civil Society Participation Index in the early 1990s, reaching 0.86 in 1990 and declining to 0.71 in 2024. In general, Estonia and Poland have stable democratic institutions and active civil society.

Figure 1. Clustering of post-communist countries by Political Rights Index (A) and Civil Liberties Index (B)
 Source: compiled by the author according to²⁹

European integration and membership of most of these countries in the European Union (further – EU) and North Atlantic Treaty Organization (further – NATO) have contributed to democratic change, the establishment of the rule of law and the protection of human rights. Poland was preparing for accession in 1991-2004 from signing the

²⁹ V-Dem Institute. (n.d.). *Id.*

Association Agreement in 1991, applying for membership in 1994 to joining in 2004. The Czech Republic submitted its application for EU membership in 1996 and joined the EU in 2004. In 1995, the Lithuania applied to join the EU and officially acceded in 2004. It is worth noting that it was the EU's requirements for Lithuania in terms of convergence indicators that stimulated its development and ensured accession negotiations in 2000-2002. In 1995, the Latvian government applied for EU membership, accession negotiations began in 1998, and the country became an EU member in 2004. In 1995, Estonia signed both an Association Agreement and a free trade agreement with the EU.

The formation of an independent judiciary, legislative and executive branches of government has ensured institutional stability, and public administration reforms through European integration have contributed to transparency and accountability of the CEE authorities. The establishment of anti-corruption mechanisms through the introduction of European regulatory standards, including in the financial sector, and continuous legislative improvements have helped maintain an appropriate level of democracy. This has also increased the level of citizen participation in political life.

The countries with transitional/hybrid political regimes include Georgia, Moldova, Serbia, and Ukraine, where democratic transformation processes are highly dependent on the state of completion of democratic reforms and changes in public administration, internal political instability and frequent changes of governments, a hybrid political system, external pressure and influence of foreign governments, interference in domestic politics, and insufficient rule of law.

Democratic change in these countries began in the 1990s, but constant setbacks to democracy due to political crises, corruption, Russia's policy of revanchism and expansionism, and hybrid aggression have led to a slowdown in democratic transformation. This has also resulted in slow legal changes and low levels of public trust in state institutions, limited public participation in political processes, corruption at all levels of government, and insufficient independence of judges. Russia's external pressure has greatly complicated institutional development and the establishment of extractive institutions that limit political participation, hinder innovation and economic growth.

In countries with transitional/hybrid political regimes, the participation of CS in political life has been growing since the early 1990s. In Georgia, Serbia, and Ukraine, the estimates of public involvement in 1990 were approximately the same (0.233, 0.179, 0.17, respectively), while Moldova had a much higher level of participation (0.603). In 2024, the level of citizens' resilience and engagement in the life of the countries increased significantly (Georgia 0.616, Moldova 0.777, Serbia 0.531, Ukraine 0.762).

The countries with authoritarian regimes include Belarus, Russia, Kazakhstan, and Uzbekistan, which have very low political rights and civil liberties due to their post-Soviet authoritarian legacy and values. There is no or weak democratic transition in these countries, and power is concentrated in the hands of the president with limited parliamentary oversight. Freedom of speech is severely restricted, and the influence of civil society organizations on democratic change is low or non-existent (Figure 2). These countries are focused on partnerships and expanding political ties with authoritarian models of government (China). Accordingly, the level of autonomy of

citizens' actions is low or below average. The civil society participation index in 2024 was 0.124 in Belarus, 0.462 in Kazakhstan, 0.142 in Russia, and 0.337 in Uzbekistan.

The grouping of post-communist countries by the level of development of democracy and civil society demonstrates that the development of civil society, its sustainability, and autonomy generally correspond to democratic development (Table 2). Countries with a high level of democratic values are characterized by a high or medium degree of autonomy of CS, civil liberties and absence of restrictions on private and political freedoms, deliberative decision-making processes of political regimes, and a high level of consideration of citizens' opinions in elections.

Table 2. Grouping of countries by the level of development of democracy and civil society

Level of democracy	Group of post-communist countries	Civil Society Participation Index	Civil Liberties Index	Deliberative Democracy Index	Electoral Democracy Index
High level of democracy	Estonia, Lithuania, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Latvia, Poland, Romania, Croatia	High (0.732)	High (0.862)	Average (0.591)	High (0.753)
Medium level of democracy, transitional/hybrid regimes	Georgia, Moldova, Serbia, Ukraine	Average (0.571)	High (0.748)	Average (0.344)	Average (0.489)
Countries with authoritarian regimes	Belarus, Russia, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan	Low (0.337)	Average (0.467)	Low (0.134)	Low (0.264)

Source: compiled by the author according to³⁰

Note: index scores are calculated for the period 1990-2024 based on the average value for each group of countries

On the other hand, countries that are undergoing a long transition to democratic values are characterized mainly by average estimates of the values of all indices for the period 1990-2024. This indicates that there have been achievements in increasing the level of autonomy of CSOs, eliminating physical violence by the government, and lifting restrictions on private and political freedoms. Since the early 1990s, the degree of deliberative decision-making in the state system has been increasing, the common good

³⁰ V-Dem Institute. (n.d.). *Id.*

and interests of the population are increasingly taken into account in public administration, and electoral competition is growing.

In countries dominated by authoritarian regimes, the level of autonomy of the CS and its participation in decision-making processes is generally quite low.

In general, the results indicate that in CEE post-communist countries, civic participation can influence the path of transition to a democratic regime. In addition, the results confirm the widening divide between democratic countries in CEE and the increasingly authoritarian post-Soviet region³¹. It is worth noting that Polish citizens did not significantly support EU accession due to numerous risks to the internal economic space. Ukraine's transition to democratic values has been complex, with active citizen participation and influence on the government's decision to join the EU in 2014. Moldova and Georgia, although characterized by a significant level of civil society activity, have had their democratization processes hampered by Russia's significant interference in their internal affairs.

In Georgia, CSOs were instrumental in organizing and mobilizing protests. Following the ousting of semi-authoritarian leaders, reform-minded governments assume power. However, the nature of civil society's engagement with the new administration differed significantly. Notably, many former civil society leaders in Georgia transitioned into roles within the new government³².

In general, some of the post-communist countries have quickly implemented transitional justice measures and successfully democratized. However, despite the establishment of independent justice mechanisms, a number of post-communist countries lack democratization progress and have low participation of CSOs in the political life of the country. On the other hand, Estonia, Lithuania, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Latvia, Poland, Romania, and Croatia have successfully consolidated democracy despite not taking such rapid measures (e.g., Estonia). In contrast, post-Soviet countries failed to democratize (e.g. Belarus)³³.

Post-communist states that are still in the process of democratization ideologically and structurally fragmented³⁴. There is a lack of consensus in the respective countries regarding the liberal state role as a deliverer of public goods and an inclusive form of citizenship. Meanwhile, the non-state sector in post-communism context is broadening towards both liberal and illiberal ways³⁵.

³¹ Foa, R. S., & Ekiert, G. (2016). *Id.*

³² Pinckney, J., Butcher, C., & Braithwaite, J. M. (2022). Organizations, resistance, and democracy: How civil society organizations impact democratization. *International Studies Quarterly*, 66(1), sqab094. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isq/sqab094>

³³ Kalemaj, I. (2021). Transitional justice and democratic consolidation in post-communist Eastern Europe: Romania and Albania. *Eastern Journal of European Studies*, 12(1), 81-103. <https://doi.org/10.47743/ejes-2021-0104>

³⁴ Belei S., Lopatynskiy Y., Lahodyn N., Nezhyd Y., Petrukha N. (2024). The Role of Uneven Agricultural Business Growth in Shaping the Socioeconomic Landscape of Rural Regions. *AD ALTA*, 14(2/XLV), 212–218. https://www.magnanimitas.cz/ADALTA/140245/papers/G_31.pdf

³⁵ Kostovicova, D. (2006). *Id.*

In general, the civil society development is a critical factor in the democratic transformation of post-communist countries that are not significantly influenced by external actors and have chosen the European democratic path of development. The latter factor mediates both democratic transformations and the civil sector raise, and its participation in building the country's democratic system.

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³⁶ Foa, R. S., & Ekiert, G. (2016). *Id.*

³⁷ Stefes, C. H., & Paturyan, Y. J. (2021). After the revolution: State, civil society, and democratization in Armenia and Georgia. *Frontiers in Political Science*, 3, 719478. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpos.2021.719478>

³⁸ Pinckney, J., Butcher, C., & Braithwaite, J. M. (2022). *Id.*

³⁹ Kalemaj, I. (2021). *Id.*

⁴⁰ Kostovicova, D. (2006). *Id.*

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DISCUSSION

5.

The grouping of post-communist countries according to the level of democracy and civil society participation in democratization from the 1990s to 2024 indicates that not only CSO activity and public consolidation play an important role in the transition process, but also the government's foreign and domestic policies. State institutions and government structures have a significant influence on the activation of CSOs in a country, as they can both stimulate their participation in political life and exert political pressure on activists and CSO members. In countries with a high degree of democratization, citizens have an active and stable position and are highly involved in political decision-making. Countries with hybrid regimes, where internal and external political pressure is exerted on citizens, are characterized by lengthy processes of reforming the state bureaucratic apparatus and democratic transition, as well as the slow establishment of European values. Therefore, in general, the scientific approach that posits the weakness of civil society in post-communist countries^{41, 42, 43} does not fully reflect the national characteristics of public participation in the political life of different post-communist countries. This may be primarily due to government influence on citizen activity. The granting of a range of political rights to citizens directly correlates with civil liberties in post-communist countries. A more realistic position is that there are differences in the degree of CS influence in the post-communist space during periods of transition⁴⁴. This view is also shared by Stan⁴⁵, who points to differences in the development of civic participation and activism in countries with "old" post-communist regimes and legacies.

⁴¹ Guasti, P. (2016). *Id.*

⁴² Chimiak, G. (2021). *Id.*

⁴³ Pierobon, C. (2021). *Id.*

⁴⁴ Bernhard, M., & Kaya, R. (2012). *Id.*

⁴⁵ Stan, L. (2012). *Id.*

CONCLUSION

6.

The study demonstrates that there is a link between a high level of democracy (Estonia, Lithuania, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Latvia, Romania, Poland, Croatia) and a high level of CSO involvement in the political system, resilience and active citizenship. In countries that have chosen the European course of development, despite the support of the population, democratic transition has been faster and the political situation has stabilized. Instead, in countries where there is external political pressure and involvement (Ukraine, Moldova, Serbia, Georgia), the active role of society contributed to reforms, although these countries are still in the process of transition and the establishment of democratic values. Civil society in countries with hybrid regimes acts as an agent of pressure on the authorities and support for reforms, but is limited by internal political instability and external influence. At the same time, the role of civil society in these countries is growing, despite a significant gap with countries with a high degree of democratization. The influence of CSOs in this region remains at an average level, in the form of public control, digitalization and development of e-democracy, and anti-corruption initiatives. The absence of an independent judiciary hinders the development of CS. In countries with authoritarian regimes, the civil society contribution is rather limited, which causes both its weak influence on making political decisions and the weakness of the democratic transition, as well as repressive policies towards civic activists.

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